

Initial dissolution profile and kinetics of glasses for bio applications

Dagmar Galusková¹, Hana Kaňková¹, Anna Švančárková¹, Si Chen¹ and Dušan Galusek¹

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass,
Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 91150 Trenčín, Slovakia
(dagmar.galuskova@tnuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

The dissolution studies of bioactive glasses and ceramics are usually performed at the static conditions and evaluation of dissolution rely on data from the following time interval 1, 3, 7 and 14 days. The compositional changes of immersion solution in first minutes and hours of biomaterial leaching are usually not addressed. However, the early stage of dissolution provides valuable information about leaching kinetics and represent one of the most important part in case of controlled release of ions into the aqueous solution. Solutions simulating body fluid (SBF) are usually buffered with TRIS to maintain the pH ~7 and are used as a leaching media for prediction of dissolution behavior of bioactive glasses [1][2].

A continuous flow measurement recording the ion release online (*inline test*) with the optical emission spectrometer with inductively coupled plasma (ICP OES) has been studied with respect to the initial dissolution. The fresh leaching solution was pumped continuously through a cell, filled with powder glass sample reflecting the composition of Bioglass 45S5 23Na₂O, 23CaO, 6P₂O₅, 48SiO₂ (wt%) and with addition of boron and zinc as ions with possible therapeutic effect. The intensities of measured signals for particular ions are quantified by comparison with calibration standards of known concentration.

The corrosion cell was tempered at the temperature 37°C in thermostatic bath. The concentration of dissolved ions and pH of input SB solution are constant during inline test, the ions released from the glass powder are measured on the output of the reaction cell. The concentration above detection limit is included in calculation and the amount of released ions normalized to their content in glass will be discussed for evaluation of mechanisms of dissolution of bioactive glasses. The limits of detection of studied therapeutic ions were published in [2]. Both type of tests need to be included in testing the bio-response. The static test give answer for apatite formation ability of tested bioactive glass system, whereas the flow through and inline tests address the initial release of ions. The initial concentration of metals released to human body could trigger therapeutic healing or could become toxic for cells.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The static tests were performed only in SBF prepared according [1]. 10 mg of sample was leached in 15 ml SBF. The tubes with sample and leaching solution were placed into the thermostatic bath set to 37°C for 1, 3 and 7 days. After the test the final solution was filtered to separate undissolved particles and its elemental chemical composition was measured by ICP OES.

Normalized leached amount of ions was calculated applying the following equation (1):

$$NL_i(t) = \frac{c_i * V}{w_i * m} \quad (1)$$

where c_i is concentration of element measured in leaching solution in time and subtracted from the blank (concentration of element in the input SBF solution), V is a volume of the leaching solution, w_i is a weight fraction of element i in sample, m is weight of sample.

For the flow-through inline test the thermostatic bath, corrosion cell, peristaltic pump and tubing were assembled and connected directly to the introduction system of the optical emission spectrometer (ICP OES 5100 SVDV, Agilent). Internal standard scandium (10 mg/L) was included in inline sampling in order to deal with non-spectral interferences.

Dissolution of borosilicate glass with different content of boron and cobalt prepared in FunGlass

Centre by dr. Si Chen were tested. As a leaching medium were used simulated body fluid (SBF, pH 7.4) that is frequently used in leaching bioactivity tests, TRIS (tris-(hydroxymethyl) aminomethane) buffer set pH to the value 7.4 at the temperature 36.5°C.

Inline tests were conducted with 100 mg of sample soaked in approx. 1 mL volume cell, through which continuously flew fresh leaching solution at the temperature held constant at 37 ± 1 °C. Concentration of Ca, B, Co, P, Si as function of time was directly monitored using ICP software. Data from dissolution of sample were monitored every 2 minutes for 1.5 hours. The total amount of leached elements (NL_i) is determined by the following equation (2) as cumulative release of particular ion:

$$NL_i(t) = c_i \frac{F}{w_i * m} \Delta t + NL_i^{t-\Delta t} \quad (2),$$

where c_i is concentration of particular leached element in time t , F is the flow rate, w_i is weight ratio of element i in sample. Values of the initial leaching rate may be evaluated from the experimental time dependencies of NL_i [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the Fig. 1 is plotted the release of cobalt under static and dynamic (*inline measurement of Co*) condition for the initial stage of glass dissolution. The ion is released linearly already in the first minutes and after one day the rate decreases to zero. The slope of linear curve detected from inline dynamic tests differs from the slope acquired by plotting the static tests from zero time. The element concentration measured at the static conditions were constant for the whole time interval. It means that equilibrium was already achieved during the first day.

Fig. 1: Release of cobalt from borosilicate glass in the initial time of immersion to SB fluid under static and dynamic (inline) test conditions at 37°C.

Fig. 2: Release of cobalt from borosilicate glass of various composition to SB fluid under static conditions at 37°C.

Evaluation of obtained data based on concentration is indicative for how much ion is released to human environment. Therefore, the information obtained from inline minute tests addresses the initial dissolution performance of material in SB fluid, such information can become crucial in respect of cytotoxicity. However, evaluation of data based on concentration do not provide relevant information about mechanism of dissolution of glass especially with different structural and compositional characteristics. The studied system of borosilicate glass with different addition of cobalt and boron dissolved in the comparable mechanism based on evaluation of data from the static test (Fig. 2).

CONCLUSIONS

Both type of tests need to be included in testing the bio-response. The static test give answer for apatite formation ability of tested bioactive glass system, whereas the flow through and inline tests address the initial release of ions. The initial concentration of metals released to human body could trigger therapeutic healing or could become toxic for cells. To discuss mechanism of dissolution of glasses of different composition and structure, the amounts of released ions normalized to their content in studied system need to be considered according to either static eq. (1) or dynamic eq. (2) conditions.

Keywords: bioactive glass, dynamic test, SBF,

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